

Impact of Artificial Intelligence on the Purchase Intention of Smart Fashion Products

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Abstract

Background: Technological advances have brought about drastic changes in many aspects of humanity, especially in business production and consumer buying behaviour. Understanding consumers' perceptions of the application of artificial intelligence (AI) in fashion product purchasing is a fascinating topic currently receiving attention from many scientists, business professionals, and related fields.

Objective: The study multidimensionally explained the behaviour of using AI technology to purchase fashion products, using a combination of the cognition–affect–behaviour paradigm and the technology acceptance model.

Methodology: The study's design was a descriptive survey, with a structured questionnaire as the instrument for data collection. SPSS software version 23 and AMOS version 24 were used to analyse the data. Data were obtained from 278 young consumers in Vietnam.

Results: Analysis results show that AI technology positively affects consumers' intentions to purchase smart fashion products through perceived usefulness and concerns about personal information security. What is especially interesting is that consumers perceive the usefulness of AI technology more than they worry about personal information security in this shopping activity.

Conclusion: The research concludes that AI is essential in smart fashion, which is one of the foundations for sustainable fashion development.

Unique contribution: The article helps propose authentic and effective measures so that consumers feel more confident and useful when buying fashion products online.

Key Recommendation: Businesses producing and trading fashion products need to take full advantage of AI applications to develop sustainable fashion. They also need to ensure the safety and security of consumers' personal information, increase trust, and help them feel the usefulness that AI brings.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Smart fashion, Cognition affect, behaviour paradigm, Sustainable consumption.

Introduction

The development of AI technology contributes to promoting the trend of smart fashion consumption by providing effective and sophisticated technologies to balance profits with environmental concerns (Caneloro, 2020). Integrating AI into these initiatives is critical, impeding the industry's shift from a revenue-focused focus to green practices. This allows brands to forecast demand more precisely, thereby minimising surplus in production, enhancing the overall traceability of the supply chain, and giving rise to customised marketing campaigns that demonstrate the brand's adherence to sustainability. Technological transition serves as the foundation for the transformation of the fashion industry, from "fast fashion" trends to sustainable business models, environmentally sustainable practices, and more responsibility (Apetrei et al., 2024).

For consumers, AI applications have a significant supporting impact on clothing selection and purchasing. The functions of style checking and advising on the product's materials provide consumers with professional recommendations that will aid their decision-making by highlighting the most environmentally friendly and trendy clothing. These functions have helped increase

consumers' efficiency in choosing clothes that suit their needs, tastes, and fashion trends. Therefore, consumers have positive attitudes toward AI fashion products. Simultaneously, information security is an unprecedented threat, and information security problems have become increasingly serious (Liu, 2022). Some scholars have confirmed the existence of this issue; however, different people have different perceptions of personal information security because it is associated with education level, environment, experience, work, and other factors (Liang & Qin, 2019). There are currently no studies investigating the impact of AI on perceived usefulness and its significant impact on the security of consumers' personal information in an emerging economy like Vietnam. In particular, no studies have used a combination of the cognition-affect-behaviour paradigm (CAB) and the technology acceptance model (TAM) to explain in a reasonable and multidimensional way the behaviour of using AI technology in purchasing fashion products.

Therefore, this study provides an overview and provides specific evidence about the feelings of smart fashion consumers. From there, propose authentic and effective measures to make them feel more confident and useful when shopping online. At the same time, it helps promote the development of smart fashion and sustainable fashion.

Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

The Cognition – Affect – Behaviour (CAB) Paradigm and Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

This study also uses TAM to explain the impact of perceived usefulness on consumers' intentions to purchase smart fashion products. TAM is one of the most commonly used theories in the study of technology user behaviour. This model helps explain the factors that motivate users to adopt and use new technology, including AI. Park and Kim (2014) applied TAM to understand user acceptance of technology applications in retail (Park & Kim, 2014). Chau and Deng (2018) applied the technology acceptance model to evaluate consumers' behavioural intentions and online shopping choices (Chau & Deng, 2018). In this study, TAM is used to explain the mediating relationship between consumers' perceived usefulness in the relationship between artificial intelligence technology and their intention to buy smart fashion products.

The combination of CAB and TAM helps explain, in a reasonable and multidimensional way, the behaviour of using or accepting technology in smart fashion shopping. In particular, CAB is very useful in comprehensive research on cognition, while TAM has advantages in behavioural research related to information technology applications. Therefore, to take advantage of these two theories, the project used both as a basis to explain the intermediate relationship between perceived usefulness and security of consumers' personal information when using AI to buy smart fashion products.

Hypothesis Development

Artificial intelligence technology and consumers' perceived usefulness

Artificial intelligence is currently developing at an exponential rate, bringing important significance to predicting consumer attitudes and behaviors towards AI. These studies suggest that consumers appreciate the functions promoted by AI products, thanks to which they can easily choose trendy outfits. Consumers who are interested in technology are more likely to try new technologies.

Perceived usefulness is “the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system will improve his or her job performance” (Davis, 1989). Perceived usefulness in the technology acceptance model has shown positive consumer attitudes toward technology use. The usefulness of AI is revealed when data is collected and shared among consumers examining fashion products, as is the case with Farfetch. The latter is an online luxury fashion platform that informs users about the footprint of fashion products. From the above, consumers can be positive toward smart fashion products. Therefore, we propose the following research hypothesis:

H₁: Artificial intelligence technology positively affects consumers' perceived usefulness.

Artificial intelligence technology and the security of consumers' personal information

Information security is the prevention of the use, access, disclosure, sharing, dissemination, recording, or destruction of information without the permission of the owner. In the current era, information security has become one of the most important issues in society, affecting many fields such as natural sciences, engineering, economics, and culture. Many scholars also affirm that, with the continuous development of the Internet and online shopping, the phenomenon of online shopping fraud is also common, and the leakage of personal information has become the main cause of online fraud. Raising consumer awareness about information security and protecting the safety of consumers' personal information has become an important issue to be resolved in the current development of online shopping (Liu, 2022). Therefore, a qualitative and quantitative study on the impact of AI on consumers' personal information security is extremely necessary, so we propose the following research hypothesis:

H₂: Artificial intelligence technology has a positive effect on the security of consumers' personal information.

Consumers' perceived usefulness and intention to purchase

Perceived usefulness is when someone perceives that the technology benefits the work they want to do. They will tend to accept and use that technology. Perceived usefulness is considered an important factor in the technology acceptance model and has been widely studied in the adoption of new technologies (Nishitani et al., 2021).

Unlike traditional services, online services are found to be a great motivator for consumers because of their unique characteristics of new technological usefulness. Shoppers can use it even when they don't have transportation and avoid crowded parking lots or bad weather. Therefore, when consumers feel the usefulness of new technological services, their intention to use them is greater, and vice versa. Online shopping will bring convenience to consumers; they are no longer limited in time and location when shopping. With the above arguments, we propose the following hypothesis:

H₃: Consumers' perceived usefulness has a positive influence on their intention to purchase smart fashion products.

Consumers personal information security and purchase intention

Information and communication technologies have increased business performance thanks to modernized sentient machines with multiple thinking capabilities. While consumers greatly benefit from this technological development, they also face the risk of losing personal information

security. AI-enabled business trends have attracted the attention of researchers exploring the factors that drive consumer behavior and online repurchase intentions (Garg et al., 2020). Since consumers regularly spend a lot of time (5 to 6 hours) on social networking sites, AI technology can help businesses track consumer behavior used to understand their purchasing process. AI is increasingly easier to implement in business practices due to the rise of big data (Samara et al., 2020). Regarding this issue, from the perspective of consumer perception, almost no research has been conducted. If consumers feel secure with their personal information, will they actively buy smarter fashion products? Therefore, this paper will fill the gap in current research by testing the following hypothesis:

H₄: The security of consumers' personal information has a positive influence on their intention to purchase smart fashion products.

Previously, researchers have confirmed a positive relationship between perceived usefulness of use and consumers' attitudes toward technology (Lunney et al., 2016). The importance of perceived usefulness was emphasised in TAM. Many scholars have also applied TAM to evaluate consumers' behavioural intentions and online shopping choices and better to understand user acceptance of technology applications in online retailing. In this article, TAM is used to explain the mediating relationship between consumers' perceived usefulness in the relationship between artificial intelligence technology and their intention to purchase smart fashion products. Therefore, we propose the following hypothesis:

H₅: Consumers' perceived usefulness plays a mediating role between artificial intelligence technology and the purchase intention of smart fashion products.

Online shopping brings convenience and many great benefits to the majority of Internet users: saving time, easily comparing prices, diversifying products, etc. However, in addition to these conveniences, online shopping also has many potential risks regarding the security of users' personal information, affecting both buyers and sellers. This study uses the CAB model to gain a deeper understanding of the relationship between AI technology applications and Vietnamese consumers' intention to purchase fashion products. The CAB model suggests that cognition (C) of the tendency to buy smart fashion products determines emotions (A) about the security of personal information, thereby influencing behavior (B) toward buying their products. Based on the CAB model, the article researches the application of AI in shopping for fashion products in Vietnam, and we see that the security of consumers' personal information when purchasing smart fashion products is being affected. Along with the acceleration of activities that take advantage of and steal consumers' personal information, this can lead to their skepticism about this form of shopping, thereby affecting their intention to purchase. Therefore, it is necessary to carefully consider issues related to consumer information security to limit its negative effects on purchase intention. From the above arguments, we make the following hypothesis:

H₆: Consumers' personal information security plays a mediating role between artificial intelligence technology and the purchase intention of smart fashion products.

Through the above analysis, the proposed research model is as shown in Figure 1:

Figure 1. Proposed research model

Research Methodology

Research Measures

The questionnaire is designed to assess the impact of consumers' perceptions of the application of artificial intelligence (AI) in purchasing fashion products. To better suit the majority of surveyed Vietnam's young consumers, the questionnaire was translated into Vietnamese. Additionally, experts reviewed the translation to ensure accuracy and that respondents wouldn't have any trouble answering. We used five-point Likert scales to represent different levels of agreement (1 = "strongly disagree," 2 = "disagree," 3 = "neutral," 4 = "agree," 5 = "strongly agree"). The proposed research model has 4 scales, specifically as follows: The Artificial Intelligence Technology scale includes 8 observed variables by Capatina et al. (2020); Consumers' perceived usefulness includes 6 observed variables by Cho and Fiorito (2009); Consumer personal information security includes 5 observed variables by Liu (2022); Intention to purchase smart fashion products includes 4 observed variables by Nguyen et al. (2019) (Capatina et al., 2020; Cho & Fiorito, 2009; Liu, 2022; Nguyen et al., 2019).

Data Collection

The article uses a non-probability sampling method with an online survey method in Vietnam. After 2 weeks, the study received 345 answer sheets. After carefully checking and eliminating unusual votes, 278 valid votes remained. The study includes 4 scales with a total of 23 observed variables, so 278 survey questionnaires are a guaranteed number to conduct CB SEM analysis. Of the 278 survey participants, more than half were female, accounting for 67.3%, and the majority were between 18 and 35 years old, accounting for 75.9%. There are differences in the occupations of survey participants, the majority of whom are students, accounting for 63.3%, office and mental workers for 25.9%, and the rest are other subjects. More than half of the surveyed people do not have monthly income, accounting for 56.8%; income under 5 million VND accounts for 30.9%; and the remaining income is from 5 to 15 million VND.

Results

Confirmatory factor analysis

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is a test used to evaluate the overall fit of the data based on model fit indices such as CMIN/df, CFI, TLI, GFI, RMSEA (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988; Baumgartner & Homburg, 1996). CFA will evaluate whether the observed variables within the scale are appropriate and meet the standards. According to the analysis results, CMIN/df=2.734, CFI=0.957, TLI=0.950, GFI=0.85, and RMSEA=0.079, the model fits the survey data.

Covariance-Based SEM analysis

Measurement model

The CB SEM model includes four variables: artificial intelligence technology, perceived usefulness, consumer personal information security, and purchase intention. First of all, to evaluate the measurement model, it is necessary to evaluate the reliability and convergent validity of the scale. Reliability was assessed by the outer loading coefficient for observed variables, Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, and composite reliability. Standardized regression weight must be greater than or equal to 0.7, Cronbach's Alpha coefficient and composite reliability (CR) must be greater than or equal to 0.7 (Hair et al., 2010). Convergent validity was assessed using the average variance extracted (AVE). The AVE coefficient must be greater than or equal to 0.5 to confirm convergent validity (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

According to the analysis results in Table 1, all standardized regression coefficients, Cronbach's alpha values, composite reliability (CR), and average variance extracted (AVE) values are higher than the recommended threshold (0.7, 0.7, 0.7, and 0.5, respectively), so the measurement model is accepted.

Table 1. Convergent validity and reliability

Variables	Category	Standardized regression weight	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite reliability (CR)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
PI	PI1	0.903	0.942	0.943	0.805
	PI2	0.912			
	PI3	0.910			
	PI4	0.855			
AIT	AIT1	0.840	0.963	0.963	0.764
	AIT2	0.903			
	AIT3	0.884			
	AIT4	0.846			
	AIT5	0.865			
	AIT6	0.883			
	AIT7	0.891			
	AIT8	0.869			
PU	PU1	0.855	0.970	0.970	0.845
	PU2	0.919			

	PU3	0.964			
	PU4	0.958			
	PU5	0.893			
	PU6	0.918			
	CPIS1	0.879			
	CPIS2	0.916			
CPIS	CPIS3	0.934	0.966	0.965	0.845
	CPIS4	0.928			
	CPIS5	0.936			

Source: Survey data analysis (2024)

Next, the discriminant validity of the scales was evaluated using the Fornell-Larcker criterion (1981), which is guaranteed when the square root of the AVE for each latent variable is higher than the other correlation values among others (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). The results in Table 2 show that the square root of AVE (the bold value at the top of each column) is larger than the correlations between latent variables (in each column and row), so discrimination is ensured.

Table 2. Discriminant validity

	CPIS	PI	PU	AIT
CPIS	0.919			
PI	0.657	0.897		
PU	0.649	0.892	0.919	
AIT	0.628	0.826	0.837	0.874

Source: Survey data analysis (2024)

Structural model

First, a multicollinearity assessment was performed. According to Wong (2013), multicollinearity can occur if the variance inflation factor (VIF) is greater than 5 or less than 0.2 (Wong, 2013). According to the analysis results, all VIF coefficients are below the threshold of 5, the maximum value of VIF is 1.724 and the minimum value is 1.0, showing that the latent variables do not have multicollinearity.

Table 3. Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis	Path	Standardized regression weight	T-test statistic	P value	Decision
H ₁	AIT → PU	0.840	14.899	0.000	Accepted
H ₂	AIT → CPIS	0.638	10.913	0.000	Accepted
H ₃	PU → PI	0.815	14.813	0.000	Accepted
H ₄	CPIS → PI	0.142	3.690	0.000	Accepted

Source: Survey data analysis (2024)

The results of the relationship between the variables in the model are shown in Figure 2 and Table 3. Because all hypotheses have $p < 0.05$, all hypotheses are accepted, including:

- The direct influence of artificial intelligence technology on consumers' perceived usefulness is higher than on the security of their personal information, with standardized regression coefficients of 0.840 and 0.638, respectively.
- Regarding the level of direct influence on the intention to buy smart fashion products, consumers' perceived usefulness has a higher influence than the factor of security of their personal information with the regression coefficient normalized are 0.815 and 0.142, respectively.

Source: Survey data analysis (2024)

Figure 2. CB SEM Structural model analysis result

Mediate relation

To analyze the mediating role of consumers' perceived usefulness and the security of their personal information in the relationship between artificial intelligence technology and consumers' intention to purchase smart fashion products. This study used the bootstrapping technique with a sample size of 1000. This is a technique that involves repeated sampling from the sample data set and estimates the indirect effect in each resampled data set. The bootstrapping technique is considered better than other techniques when evaluating mediated relationships because it does not require data to be normally distributed and can be applied to small sample sizes. According to the analysis results in Table 4, artificial intelligence technology affects the intention to buy smart fashion products through consumers' perceived usefulness and the security of their personal information. In particular, consumers' perceived usefulness plays a stronger mediating role than personal

information security, with indirect influence coefficients of 0.687 and 0.095, respectively. Thus, hypotheses H₅ and H₆ are also accepted.

Table 4. Summary report of indirect effects of hypotheses

Path	Indirect effect	p-value
AIT → PU → PI	0.687	0.000
AIT → CPIS → PI	0.095	0.006

Source: Survey data analysis (2024)

Discussion

This article contributes to research on smart fashion consumption trends, one of the foundations for sustainable fashion development. Previous studies suggest that AI helps consumers choose fashionable and effective outfits (Liang et al., 2020). However, consumers are worried about the security of personal information during shopping (Liu, 2022). Therefore, an overall assessment and specific evidence of smart fashion consumers' feelings of usefulness, but fear of losing personal information security, is a necessary and valuable study that can solve this problem. From there, it can help propose authentic and effective measures so that consumers feel more confident and useful when shopping online. At the same time, it helps promote the development of the smart fashion and sustainable fashion industries.

The study used a combination of CAB and TAM theories to rationally and multi-dimensionally explain technology usage and acceptance behaviour in applying AI to purchase smart fashion products. Some new initiatives to help consumers feel more confident and useful when shopping online and, at the same time, promote the development of the smart fashion and sustainable fashion industries are presented below. First, the study determined that the direct impact of AI technology on consumers' perceived usefulness is higher than on the security of their personal information. This is a new discovery on the topic, different from previous single studies on the impact of AI applications in online shopping on user acceptance of technology or information security issues (Liang et al., 2020; Liu, 2022). This brings a very positive signal in that consumers feel beneficial when buying smart fashion products, and they also feel safe when searching for information and during the online shopping process. This is understandable, as fashion companies are making great efforts to optimize business activities, aiming for sustainable development through the application of AI in everything from production and distribution to communication and sales. From there, consumers will feel that choosing fashion products will be easier, faster, more effective, and especially more environmentally friendly.

Next, regarding the level of direct influence on the intention to purchase smart fashion products, consumers' perceived usefulness has a higher influence than the security of their personal information. Similar to the above, this is also an interesting new point on the topic when it combines research on multi-dimensional consumer perceptions. Unlike traditional services, online services are found to be a great motivator for consumers because of their unique characteristics of new technological usefulness. When consumers feel the usefulness of new technological services, their intention to use them is greater, and vice versa. Online shopping will bring convenience to consumers; they are no longer limited in time and location when shopping. Once consumers are aware of and feel the excitement, fun, and benefits that social networks bring, they will use them in the future, despite the threat of personal information security.

Finally, consumers' perceived usefulness plays a stronger mediating role than their personal information security in the relationship between artificial intelligence technology and smart fashion product purchase intention. This interesting new finding is explained by combining two theories: CAB and TAM. In the past, CAB was often used to evaluate the brand selection process and shopping experience, examining the reasons for behaviour through consumer perceptions, individual and is useful in explaining the mediating effects of emotions, while TAM has advantages in behavioural research related to information technology applications. In this study, we used a combination to rationally and multidimensionally explain technology usage behaviour and acceptance in smart fashion shopping.

Conclusions and Implications

Conclusions

In the current era, AI is developing strongly and affirming its important role in the 4.0 technology revolution through many important applications in human life and society. At the same time, AI technology is strongly applied in all fields and industries, especially in the field of fashion. Issues related to the environment are becoming increasingly urgent and attracting top attention, forcing businesses to approach and apply them to the production process for sustainable and environmentally friendly development. Therefore, this research is particularly important, both theoretically and practically. The article provides an overview and provides specific evidence about the perceptions of smart fashion consumers through qualitative and quantitative research methods. This is also a rare study that combines the two theories, CAB and TAM, to explain in a reasonable and multi-dimensional way the usage behavior and acceptance of AI technology in smart fashion shopping. From there, we have filled in the theoretical gap about the direct influence of AI technology on consumers' perceived usefulness, which is higher than personal information security. Regarding the level of direct influence on the intention to buy smart fashion products, consumers' perceived usefulness has a higher influence than the factor of security of their personal information, and especially, consumers' perceived usefulness plays a stronger mediating role than personal information security in the relationship between AI technology and the purchase intention of smart fashion products. The results of this study help confirm that the smart fashion trend is being accepted by consumers, creating motivation for the smart fashion industry to upgrade the platform, increase the security of personal information, and have a user-friendly interface. This is a solid foundation for developing green fashion.

Implications

Firstly, businesses producing and trading fashion products need to take full advantage of AI applications to develop sustainable fashion. This can be done by upgrading AI applications and in-depth consulting techniques to recommend personalized fashion styles, encouraging consumers to make sustainable fashion choices such as materials. Environmentally friendly fabric, longevity of clothing, appropriate size, and style. This not only reduces environmental impact by creating a sustainable value supply chain but also improves operational efficiency and reduces production costs.

Second, businesses need to ensure the safety and security of consumers' personal information, increase trust, and help them feel the usefulness that AI brings. The concepts of smart fashion and sustainable fashion, as well as the Vietnamese people's access to AI technology, are still not widespread. One of the reasons is that the promotion of fashion businesses is not effective. Therefore, to build trust and attract consumer interest in AI applications smartly and sustainably, businesses need to diversify communication channels and forms, creating a trend and culture of shopping for smart fashion products and making consumers no longer feel unfamiliar with this technology.

Third, businesses selling fashion products need to continuously upgrade the platform of new fashion technology products that integrate AI to have a friendly interface and optimize to attract users and create an image. Prestigious brand image and environmental protection. At the same time, upgrading features help them grasp information about the product and its impact on the environment, providing information about the origin and production process of the product and how to preserve and use fashion safely sustainable way.

Fourth, fashion businesses need to be fully equipped with AI knowledge for sales staff. Rather than being limited to personal use at home, AI fashion products could be developed in-store as a means to reduce consumer risk concerns and increase their awareness of smart fashion. Therefore, each smart fashion-savvy salesperson or chatbot to assist with purchases, predict how clothes will fit, and personalize recommendations based on style or purchase history is important.

Finally, fashion businesses need to plan the process of creating, communicating, and distributing value through AI technology in a specific and comprehensive way. They need to organize many connection programs between environmental protection and fashion associations with offices across the country; organize collaborative events, smart fashion festivals, and community events to promote and introduce products, bringing smart fashion products and applications closer to consumers. Next is to effectively use media such as social networks, radio channels, and television programs to promote smart fashion applications. Currently, fraudulent acts of disguise are taking place in an extremely complex and sophisticated manner, directly affecting businesses selling smart fashion products. This may be due to the incomplete legal framework; some businesses do not strictly comply with business ethics, in addition to great business opportunities and low competitive pressure. Therefore, the main role of the government and authorities here is to protect consumers and truly sustainable fashion businesses.

Limitations and future research directions

Besides its contributions to the smart fashion and sustainable fashion industries, this research has the following limitations: First, the study does not ensure a sample set that can represent the whole population well, especially since the majority of participants are aged 18–35 years old. Participants have known about or have experienced AI for fashion product shopping. Second, the application of AI in the fashion field in Vietnam is still limited, so document review in Vietnam as well as surveys are also difficult. Therefore, future studies can consider the application of AI in different industries, regions, and countries to compare consumer intentions in those places and generalize findings.

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